

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Municipality	x		x			
Decision makers				x		
Officers/technicians				x	x	
Researchers	x	x	x			
General Public				x		
xxx						

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	FE_UHI
Name	Urban Heat Island Estimation
Description	Estimation of surface temperatures based on satellite images (LANDSAT) over a 10-year period (2013-2023) and subsequent determination of urban heat islands also based on socio-demographic factors.
Primary User	Technicians of Municipality Ferrara (depts. Urban Planning for policies, Municipal technicians for renovations, Environment), External surveyors, architect, engineers
Goal	Identify priorities and hot spots within the urban area and take decisions to mitigate urban heat island effects
Owner	FBK-DEDA
Status	designed
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	Global warming results in warmer, drier winters, reducing rainfall and snowfall, and drying watersheds. Ferrara experiences extreme heat, with temperatures exceeding 50°C (surface temperature) and long droughts. In the city centre, which is characterised by highly built-up areas, the effect of high temperatures is particularly felt. To counterbalance the impact of

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

	<p>Urban Heat Islands, the local government has prioritised different measures encoded in policy strategies and actions.</p>
<p>Strategy/Plan/Regulation</p>	<p>Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) https://mycovenant.eumayors.eu/storage/web/mc_covenant/documents/8/sAXh5xFfETcgjxrKZmonkdBKQkKJir6s.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MGS35: GreenCity and other green area projects (action for mitigation) <p>Using territorial planning instruments, this action envisages tree planting and green areas development to contain heat island effects and consequently reduce energy consumption for cooling. Indicators for monitoring and evaluation include the number and types of trees planted and cut, and the number of deals and surfaces adopted. Based on the identified hotspots of the city, the UHI use case can support planning for this action by providing necessary data and analysis to prioritise high-risk areas for intervention.</p> <p>Integrated Regional Air Quality Plan 2030 (PAIR2030) The Action Plan, prepared by the Emilia-Romagna Region and involving 207 municipalities, defines air quality policies and measures to reduce atmospheric emissions. Among its priority areas, one specifically regards urban and lowlands areas with Action 5 aiming to expand green spaces and urban parks in municipalities with more than 30.000 inhabitants. This action foresees the distribution of trees to citizens, associations and public entities. The use case can support this action by indicating priority areas where to design urban green spaces with the greatest effect.</p>
<p>Local Green Deal / City contract(s)</p>	<p>General Urban Plan (PUG) https://www.comune.ferrara.it/pug The new General Urban Plan of the Municipality of Ferrara defines four strategic objectives; the first one aims at transforming the city into a resilient territory capable of adapting and mitigating changes and risks. The UHI use case can support the realisation of the Strategic Line 4 focused on improving air quality and urban microclimate to guarantee wellbeing conditions for the citizens and for the ecosystems. More specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Objective 1 > Strategic Line 4 > Project Action 2 <p>This action aims to reduce the heat islands' effect through the improvement of vegetation coverage, paving's replacement and reducing the proportion of albedo in the areas most exposed to the risk of rising temperatures, in order to support long-term sustainable urban development, considering adaptation to climate change.</p>
<p>European Green Deal Policy Area</p>	<p>This use case contributes to reaching the EU's climate ambition for 2030 and 2050; and achieving the priorities related to climate adaptation. The EU Strategy for Adaptation sets both the framework for achieving climate neutrality and the ambition on adaptation by 2050. The implementation of these actions aims to respond to the needs of adaptation to climate change</p>

	at the local level and the reduction of the impact of increasingly persistent hazards such as rising urban temperatures.
Precondition	
<p>Data requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping of the roofs and soil surface materials as well (identifying roads, waters, green areas etc.) - Images from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS sensors to estimate surface temperature - Georeferenced vulnerable population data (age <10 or age > 70) - Map of public services (hospitals, schools...) and attractiveness <p>Tools and algorithm:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FBK UHI DETECTION algorithm. Estimates land surface temperature raster layer at 30m from Landsat Images - FBK_UHI_vulnerability algorithm. Retrieve a vulnerability map of the population - ENVI-met - QGIS plugin Geodata2Envimet - DEDA Matching Table Envimet 	
Postcondition	
DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<p>DRI 1 Hot spot map described at https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/c998b153-071b-4dca-bf07-a734589182a5</p> <p>DRI 2 Vulnerability map UHI described at https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/1730dcd2-ec50-4612-a9e3-2f28f5951c77</p>
Use of DRI	<p>DRI 1 Identification of hot spots for urban planning and environmental analysis</p> <p>DRI 2 Vulnerability thematization supporting decision for prioritising areas for intervention. The vulnerability thematization provides information on the impacts of Urban Heat Island on specific category of people and places (busy places):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - children (under 6 years old) - elderly (over 65 years old) - schools (primary, secondary, high) - places for health and social assistance (e.g. hospitals, collective residences, ...) - squares <p>Crossing the information on hot area with the vulnerability index is possible to define the priority area where planning intervention is needed</p>
Use case processing steps	
UC FE-UHI BPMN.drawio	
Additional remarks	
DRI 1 Possibility of simulating climate mitigation interventions for the hotspots through the use of ENVI-met modelling software	

DOI to processing steps BPMN

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